

EFFECT OF DEFECT SIZE ON FATIGUE PROPERTIES FOR SiC WHISKER REINFORCED A 6061 ALUMINUM ALLOY MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The effect of defect size is discussed on the fatigue property of a composite of ductile aluminum alloy matrix and SiC whiskers reinforcements, SiCw/A6061. Fatigue tests were conducted by rotating bending in laboratory air, up to 5×10^7 cycles using smooth bar type specimens. The fatigued specimen were examined on the outer surface and on the fracture surfaces, as well, to measure the defects found as crack origins. A temporary fatigue limit was observed for polished specimen in short life range, where the fracture was attributed to surface defects. Beyond 10^7 cycles the fracture was found due to inner defects at lower stresses. Fatigue limit of unpolished specimens was dependent to the surface fracture. The stress intensity factor calculated on the basis of defect size was linearly correlated to the logarithms of number of cycles to failure, irrespective of the surface and inner fractures. Using this relationship the fatigue strength was predicted, which showed a good agreement with experimental data. The critical defect size for the surface fatigue fracture was estimated to be about $32 \mu\text{m}$ based on the fatigue threshold and the temporary fatigue limit for polished specimens.

Keywords: Metal matrix composite, Fatigue, Fractography, Defect size

1. INTRODUCTION

It is thought that for whisker or particle reinforced metal matrix composites (MMC) the mechanical properties can be more isotropic than those for long fiber reinforced ones. As the short fiber reinforced MMC can be forged, extruded or rolled by ordinary processing techniques and as it has composites have a higher specific strength than monolithic alloys, it is expected to be used for practical applications such as automobile parts. The authors ¹⁾ have reported fatigue properties and discussed mechanism of fatigue fracture on SiC whisker reinforced A2024 and SiC particle reinforced A356 and A357 alloys. They showed that the fatigue strength was increasing with increase in volume fraction of whiskers or particles, in case where the fatigue crack initiated by Stage I mechanism suggested by Forsyth²⁾

However, the fatigue strength was nearly the same as that of matrix alloys, in case of crack initiation from voids just beneath the specimen surface. Moreover, the fatigue fracture toughness, evaluated on the basis of final fatigue crack length, gradually decreased with increasing the volume fraction¹⁾. According to their results¹⁾, it is thought that the mechanical properties of short fiber reinforced MMC are closely linked to the size and location of defects in the composites.

In this paper, fatigue properties of SiC whisker reinforced aluminum alloy matrix composite are discussed in relation to the defect size at fatigue crack origin. To discard the stress concentration at the specimen fillet, a straight bar type specimen is fabricated by extrusion. As the ductility is regarded as more and more important for practical application, A6061 aluminum alloy is selected as matrix material in this study.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 MATERIALS

The SiC whisker (SiC_w) reinforced A6016 aluminum alloy matrix composite ($\text{SiC}_w/\text{A6016}$) was used in this study. The volume fraction (V_f) of SiC whisker was 10%. The composite was fabricated by powder metallurgy method. The whisker was β -SiC with average diameter of about $0.5\ \mu\text{m}$ and with original average length of about $20\ \mu\text{m}$. The whisker was blended with 300 mesh commercially available powder of A6061 aluminum alloy prepared by inert gas atomization. The composite was formed by cold compaction followed by a hot pressing at temperatures above the solidus of the matrix alloy, under degassed condition. The pressed billet material was extruded into a bar with final diameter of 4.2 mm. It was heat treated under T6 condition. Photograph 1 shows microstructure of $\text{SiC}_w/\text{A6061}$ composite in this study. In Photo. 1(a), dark areas show whisker rich zones, while white areas show whisker poor zones. The whisker rich zones are found parallel to the extruded direction.

After dissolution of the matrix in a hydrochloric acid solution at the specimen surface, SiC whiskers appear like acicular white bars parallel to the extruded direction, Photo. 1(b). Photograph 2 shows the micrograph of the specimen surface after extrusion. The horizontal direction is the extruded direction. The white area is the surface of the specimen on which the black lines are observed aligned direction. The white area is the surface of the specimen on which the black lines are observed aligned normal to the extruded direction. These black lines are small cracks formed during the extrusion. Its average length was about $120\ \mu\text{m}$. As these small cracks are expected to be fatigue origin, the specimen surface was polished with diamond paste before fatigue test.

2.2 MECHANICAL TESTS

The tensile test and fatigue test specimens were cut from the extruded bars after heat treatment. The tensile test was performed using an Instron type machine. The tensile loading speed was held constant at 0.5 mm per minute up to 0.2% proof stress and then switched to 2 mm per minute until failure. The fatigue testing machine was a rotating bending type. As the specimens were round bars of 4.2 mm in diameter, iron sleeves were used to mount them in the grip. Teflon tubes were inserted between specimen and sleeves in order to avoid stress concentration.

The tensile and fatigue fracture surfaces were examined by a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 TENSILE PROPERTIES

Tensile test results are listed in Table I. For $\text{SiC}_w/\text{A6061}$ the tensile strength and Young's modulus are about 45% and 33% higher, respectively, than those for matrix alloy referred.

3.2 FATIGUE PROPERTIES

Fatigue strengths are shown in Fig.1. The data are plotted by different marks for surface polished. After regression analysis proposed by Probit of those data the solid lines were drawn indicating in 50% failure probability response for each condition. As the fatigue strength of matrix

alloy was not obtained in this study, reference data are shown by dotted line³⁾. Moreover, the reference data for the same matrix with a volume fraction of 18% are also shown by dotted line³⁾.

In case of surface polished composite, the fatigue strength were determined for two life ranges, that is, shorter than 10^6 cycles and longer life than 10^7 cycles. For surface polished composite, a knee of S-N curve is found in the shorter life range. In the long life region the fatigue strength decreases with increasing load cycling. Fatigue strength of polished specimen is higher than that of data for SiC_w/A6061 composite with a volume fraction of $V_f=18\%$ ³⁾

For unpolished specimens of as-heat treated or as-fabricated conditions the fatigue limits are observed before 10^7 cycles. For as-heat treated composites unpolished or as-fabricated, fatigue crack initiated at the specimen surface. On the other hand, for unpolished specimen heat treated in the same condition, the results are lower than that for polished specimen. Moreover, fatigue limit for unpolished specimen is nearly equal to that of the matrix alloy referred.

3.3 FRACTOGRAPHY

Photograph 3 shows the fatigue fracture surface of polished specimen. In the short life region, Photo. 3(a) shows the fatigue crack initiated from a surface defect which is about $36\ \mu\text{m}$ in depth. In the long life region, however, it was from an inner defect beneath the specimen surface.

As mentioned above, the polished specimen showed a temporary fatigue limit. According to the fractography in Photo. 3, different fracture mechanisms operate before and after the life region at the temporary fatigue limit. If the crack does not initiate from inner defects, it is suggested that the temporary fatigue limit can not be observed for unpolished specimen. This is assumed because in case of the surface fatigue fracture a fatigue limit was found for unpolished specimen and as-fabricated specimen shown in Fig.1.

It has been reported that the inner fatigue crack initiation was observed for ultra high strength steels⁴⁾ and carburized steels⁵⁾. For those steels a temporary fatigue limit was also found. It was due to the inner crack origin and showed fish eye failure. In the long life region the fatigue strength decreased with increasing cycles continuously up to 10^9 cycles.

Similar to the tendency of fatigue behavior for ultra high strength steels and carburized steels, it is assumed that the fatigue limit can be found around 5×10^7 cycle as shown in Fig. 1. It is recommended that the fatigue test has to be continued over 10^8 cycles for these type of composite materials.

It is necessary to make clear the inner fatigue crack initiation mechanism. A higher magnification view of the fatigue crack origin has revealed that there are many acicular bars in the fatigue crack origin. Those acicular bars are silicon carbide whiskers. It is suggested that the fatigue crack initiated at the gathered silicon carbide whiskers. Local concentration of silicon carbide whiskers is due to the difficulties in elaboration process (powder metallurgy), where the reinforcements are insufficiently mixed with aluminium alloy powders. In order to improve the fatigue strength of whisker reinforced aluminum alloy matrix composites, it is very important to homogeneously disperse the reinforcements in the matrix to reduce the dense parts of fibers or particles.

On the other hand many small cracks were found on the unpolished specimen surface as shown in Photo. 2. In that case the fatigue strength was lower than that for polished specimen, as mentioned above. This explains that the fatigue crack are initiated from small defects on the surface.

3.4 DEFECT SIZE AT FATIGUE CRACK ORIGINS

As mentioned in section 3.3 the defects were observed at the fatigue crack origin. The defect size was measured on the fractographs at high magnification and the stress intensity factor evaluated.

The stress intensity factor range, ΔK , is calculated by Equation (2)

$$\Delta K = (2M/\pi) \Delta \sigma (1-2t/d) \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (2)$$

where M is a coefficient depending on the depth of crack origin from the specimen surface and $\Delta \sigma$ the stress range at that depth. The value of M is 1.12 for the surface fracture. t is the depth of fracture origin from the specimen surface as shown in Fig. 3. In this figure the data are plotted by different symbols for three types of specimens. The scatter of these data is a little large, but the difference between the three specimens conditions are small, in comparison to the fatigue strength data on S-N curves shown in Fig. 1.

The relationship between the range of stress intensity factor and number of cycles to failure is:

$$\log \Delta K = -0.0821 \log N_f + 1.005 \quad (3)$$

It is concluded that ΔK values are linearly correlated to the logarithm of number of cycles to failure, N_f . In Fig. 3 the straight line is shown after regression analysis of data. The lowest ΔK is about $2.2 \text{ Pam}^{1/2}$ and this value means the fatigue threshold.

Now the fatigue limit for surface fatigue fracture for polished specimen is considered. The fatigue limit is about 240 MPa. A defect size for surface fatigue fracture was estimated on the basis of Equation (2) and using fatigue threshold of $2.2 \text{ Pam}^{1/2}$. The critical defects size is estimated about $2a=32 \mu\text{m}$. If the defect size is less than $32 \mu\text{m}$, inner fatigue fracture can not occur.

3.5 ESTIMATION OF FATIGUE LIFE

According to the results in section 3.4 the fatigue life was predicted in two cases, for the surface fracture case and for the inner fracture case. At first for the surface fracture case, the original defect depth is $a=36 \mu\text{m}$ for surface polished specimen, while for unpolished specimen the average surface length of small cracks observed on the fractograph was evaluated as $2a=124 \mu\text{m}$. For inner fracture case, $2a=62 \mu\text{m}$ and $t=58 \mu\text{m}$ from Photo. 4(a). Values of ΔK are calculated from these results and introduced into Eq(3) to estimate fatigue life. The estimated fatigue lives are shown in Fig. 4 by several curves. Of course, the curves fit well the experimental data shown as plots. In the case of surface fracture, the fatigue strength decreases about 70% with increasing crack length from $36 \mu\text{m}$ to $62 \mu\text{m}$. At a given crack length the fatigue life is longer for inner fracture than for surface fracture. As fatigue limit is observed in case of surface fracture, it is easier to decide the fatigue strength for design.

In case of inner origin the fatigue fracture mechanism is not clear. Estimation of the fatigue limit must be carefully done. In general, the fatigue crack propagation life after initiation of crack form defects can be predicted on the basis of fatigue crack propagation properties. As we already have reported about fatigue crack propagation mechanism for $\text{SiC}_w/\text{A2024-T6}$ composite¹⁾, the fatigue crack initiation period is also very important. It is essential at lower stresses and in case of short fiber reinforced composites. The fatigue life prediction may not be accurate enough when it is based on crack propagation only. But it can be accurate enough in the case of fatigue crack initiation at the defects.

3.6 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FATIGUE STRENGTH AND TENSILE STRENGTH.

As it is not so easy to obtain the fatigue properties for composites, it is very useful to estimate the fatigue properties from other mechanical properties, such as tensile strength. The relation between fatigue strength and tensile strength have been reported for steels. There are not so many data for short fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composites obtained by ourselves, but we try to discuss it here. In Fig.5 the relationship between fatigue strength and tensile strength for composites is shown. The hollow symbols show composites data, and plus marks rolled aluminum alloys data.

Their tensile strengths are in the range from 200 to 600 MPa. The ratio of fatigue strength to tensile strength is variable, but it is around 0.33. On the other hand for composites, the ratio of fatigue to tensile strengths is about 0.42. It is clear that the fatigue strength for composites is higher than the matrix alloys at a given tensile strength. The straight line is obtained from regression analysis. The data for SiC_w/A6061 composite in this study fits well with this line.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In order to discuss the effect of the defect size at crack origin on the fatigue properties the SiC_w/A6061 based on ductile matrix alloy composites were examined. In this study straight bar type specimens were prepared to discard the stress concentration at the specimen fillet. The fatigue tests are the following:

1) The surface polished specimen has a temporary fatigue limit in the short life region, while over the number of cycles to failure of $N_f=10^7$ the fatigue strength decreases with increasing life. The specimen as-fabricated or as-heat-treated without polishing have a fatigue limit in the life region around 5×10^7 cycles. The fatigue strength at $N_f=10^7$ cycles for polished specimen is about 30% higher than that for specimen without polishing.

2) For the surface polished heat treated specimen the fatigue crack initiated from defect situated on the specimen surface, in the shorter life region, while crack initiated from inner defects where many silicon carbide whiskers gathered in the long life region over $N_f=10^7$ cycles. As a result the polished specimen has a temporary fatigue limit in the shorter life region

3) For the unpolished specimen small cracks normal to the extrusion axis were found on the specimen surface. The average length of small cracks was about 120 μ m. It is considered that those small cracks were formed during the extrusion. Polishing of the specimen surface guarantees a higher fatigue limits as the fatigue crack initiates from small surface cracks.

4) The stress intensity factor calculated on the basis of the defect sizes at crack origins were linearly related to the number of cycles to failure on log-log coordinates paper for all specimens tested in this study. The dispersion is very small in comparison to the ordinary S-N curves. The fatigue strengths predicted on the basis of this relation were in good agreement to the experimental results and the critical defect size estimated was about 32 μ m using the fatigue threshold of 2.2MPa $m^{1/2}$ and the fatigue limit of 240MPa for polished specimen.

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(a)

(b)

Photo.1 : Microstructures

Photo.2 : Observation of specimen surface

(a)

(b)

Photo.3 : Microfractographs of SiC_w/A6061 composite

Table 1 Mechanical properties

Material	Heat treat.	0.2% proof stress (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Modulus (GPa)	Vickers hardness (HV)
SiC _w /A6061 (10%)	Fab.	162	299	9.3	81.2	84
	T6	427	479	5.9	91.5	146
A6061 ¹⁾	T6	309	333	13.6	69.0	-

Fig.1 : Fatigue data for SiC_w/A6061 composite

Fig.2 : Defect shape and size

Fig.3 : Relationship between stress intensity factor and number of cycles

Fig.4 : Estimated fatigue properties

Fig.5 : Variation of fatigue strength to tensile strength